

SUPPORTING DOCUMENT

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Investigation of the use of self-cleaving intein tag including chitin binding domain in the recombinant production of MPT64, the immunogenic protein of *M. tuberculosis*

Figure S1. Digested fragment run in electrophoresis gel.

Figure S2: Digested fragment run in electrophoresis gel.

V:I 1:3

V:I 1:5

V:I 1:10

Figure S3. Pictures of agar plates after transformation of pTXB1 with insert into *E.coli* ER2566 at different V:I ratios.

V:I 1:3

V:I 1:5

V:I 1:10

Figure S4. Pictures of agar plates after transformation of pTYB21 with insert into *E.coli* ER2566 at different V:I ratios.

Figure S5. Image of gel electrophoresis after colony PCR.

Figure S6. Image of gel electrophoresis after colony PCR.